

EOSC Denmark Coordination Forum

Activities and reflections 2025

Mandated Organisation
of the EOSC Association

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Danish e-Infrastructure Consortium (DeiC)

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Table of contents

- 1. The Danish EU Presidency hosting EOSC meetings..... 3
- 2. Updates from the EOSC Association 4
- 3. DeiC engagement in EOSC projects 2025 5
- 4. Ongoing and upcoming EOSC projects with DeiC involvement 7
- 5. A selection of current EOSC projects..... 9
- 6. Stakeholder and use case library10
- 7. Future plans and reflections.....11

1. The Danish EU Presidency hosting EOSC meetings

As part of the Danish EU Presidency, the Danish Agency for Higher Education and Science hosted the EOSC Steering Board (SB) meeting as well as the EOSC Tripartite meeting, which in addition to the EOSC SB includes the EOSC Association and the European Commission.

The meetings focused on the ongoing development of EOSC, a shared European digital and secure infrastructure for research data sharing. From the official Danish agency news feeds, we are told that Denmark plays a central role in EOSC and the new digital platform for sharing research data. Central to EOSC is the goal of creating a coherent European ecosystem for research data, strengthening Europe's competitiveness and digital sovereignty. The initiative aims to make it easier for researchers and businesses – across disciplines and borders – to find, access, and reuse data. The ambition is to support interdisciplinary research collaboration and innovation within fields such as health, climate, and technology.

The meetings in Copenhagen on 27–28th of November focused on future governance and financing of EOSC under the new research framework programme, Horizon Europe (2028–2034), the continued practical development of EOSC, and the need to preserve and share European data in a secure environment.

The Danish Agency for Higher Education and Science opened the meeting with a keynote by the agency's director, Mikkel Leihardt, who highlighted the meetings' historical setting:

“Just as Eigtveds Pakhus once connected Denmark to global trade, the EOSC collaboration aims to connect Europe's research communities, enabling cooperation, data sharing, and scientific progress across borders.”

The agency will continue its work with EOSC in 2026 as a member of the EOSC SB, which includes EU member states, while DeiC will continue to represent Denmark in the EOSC Association, where EOSC users – such as universities – are represented.

2. Updates from the EOSC Association

[EOSC](#) is a European framework arising from EU policies and strategies, operating under the European Commission, with the Danish Agency for Higher Education and Science represented on the [EOSC Steering Board](#). EOSC aims to create a European federated digital infrastructure for publishing, finding, and reusing data, tools, and services for research, innovation, and education. The driving motivation is rooted in the principles of Open Science ([OS](#)) and [FAIR data](#), in particular the idea of increased research efficiency and improved competitiveness (currently described in the [Draghi report](#)). EOSC pursues this goal through better access to data, the standardisation of research policies and the integration of research tools and services. Work is being done to achieve freer movement of data and services across national borders. Consequently, there is an expectation that Denmark, through DeiC, will both provide and utilise European e-infrastructures, tools, and services.

EOSC is being implemented through a collaborative federation ([the EOSC Federation](#)) consisting of nodes ([EOSC Nodes](#)). At the moment, 13 EOSC candidate nodes are being established – both thematic, multi-country, and national. Several are already actionable, including:

- The Polish Candidate Node: <https://eosc.pl/>
- The Finnish Candidate Node: <https://research.csc.fi/eosc-the-finnish-candidate-node/>
- The Czech Candidate Node: <https://www.eosc.cz/en>
- The Data Terra Candidate Node: <https://www.data-terra.org/eosc/>

In collaboration among the EOSC Association and representatives for the candidate the [EOSC Federation Handbook](#) is currently elaborated and key challenges such as trust&identity and interoperability are addressed. In Denmark, the operational implementation of EOSC falls under DeiC, which serves as the national provider of research infrastructure. Currently this is anchored in the National Strategy for Data Management based on the FAIR principles ([the FAIR Strategy](#)).

Going forward, Danish participation in EOSC will require:

- That Danish digital research assets are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR), based on EOSC's strategic ambitions for interoperability, standardisation, and technological convergence.
- A strengthened national collaboration on e-infrastructure, tools, and services for research, innovation, and education across research institutions and European borders.
- Secure machine access to Danish research data (Machine Accessibility & Actionability) to support artificial intelligence (AI Readiness).

DeiC aims to enhance its internationalisation—that is, to strengthen collaboration both within Denmark and across national borders, for example by:

- Deepening national cooperation on research data and digital infrastructure.
- Increasing international engagement and co-funding of EU-led initiatives (e.g., Horizon Europe, Digital Europe, EOSC, EuroHPC JU, Common Data Spaces, the AI Continent Action Plan, ESFRIs, and ERICs, among others).

EOSC Symposium 2025

This year's EOSC Symposium demonstrated increased engagement and commitment from the European Commission to the EOSC rationale and its implementation. Marc Lemaître, Director-General of DG RTD, addressed a global audience representing 36 countries with a strong statement: *"You can count on the full support of the European Commission in this vital and transformative endeavour. Let's make it happen!"*. A key priority is achieving European agreement on a new engaging and sustainable governance and financial model for the EOSC Federation.

The opening day presented the first wave of EOSC Federation Nodes, which signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with the EOSC Association, marking the beginning of a new era for the Federation — a shared infrastructure connecting European research organisations, data spaces, and services.

Robbert Dijkgraaf, President of the International Science Council, called for a *"Research and Innovation Union"* in Europe- one that will align national policies, strategies, instruments, and networks across EU countries, directly challenging the scientific dominance of the US and China. The need for more accessible FAIR data flows across European borders is evident. Supporting standardisation and infrastructure is therefore essential, and this is ultimately a political matter. Politics, however, is downstream from culture. European culture has already demonstrated its ability to foster political and economic collaboration. So, we must and can make EOSC happen.

The second day's discussions focused on the future development of the EOSC Federation — how to interconnect national nodes, align technical and organisational frameworks, and strengthen the growing community. A new call for the second wave of EOSC Federation Nodes was announced, including a cascading grant under the EOSC Gravity project designed to support the Federation's growth. Among the call's objectives is support for preparatory work for future Candidate EOSC Nodes, including assistance with project charters to underpin future applications for node creation (national, multi-country, or thematic).

The final day of the Symposium focused on federating competencies and skills development, FAIR data, and artificial intelligence. Subsequent panels explored digital sovereignty, engagement of innovators and start-ups, and the training of a new generation of data stewards and researchers equipped to thrive in an open and collaborative scientific environment.

3. DeIC engagement in EOSC projects 2025

This section details completed EOSC projects with DeIC involvement in 2025.

FAIR IMPACT

The FAIR-IMPACT project sought to implement the FAIR principles across scientific communities, stakeholder groups, and institutions.

Outputs

- Over 120 teams from 29 countries were supported via three open calls, distributing €500,000 and involving more than 90 organisations.
- 150 documented implementation stories showcasing FAIR principles in action: [FAIR-IMPACT Implementation Stories](#)
- Publication of 18 FAIR [Use Cases](#) across disciplines, and National roadshows showcasing FAIR implementation across 14 EU countries, and webinars on FAIR implementation, all still available online: [Workshops](#)

Impact and reflections

FAIR-IMPACT strengthened a more open European research environment by connecting diverse actors and fostering collaborations. The *Open calls* allowed participants to learn, share experiences, and build capacity. For Denmark, the participating universities and DeIC gained insight into international developments in data management and FAIR principles and represented Danish perspectives in European discussions on standards and data governance. In the future, we hope and aim to increase participation from Danish universities in EOSC calls.

Agneta Ghose, assistant professor at AAU on participating in the open call *FAIRness assessment challenge for datasets and semantic artefacts*:

"I think the FAIR IMPACT project was very useful for me as it pushed me to try and find possibilities to enhance FAIR data sharing as well as raise its need in the domain of environmental assessment - particularly data used for Life cycle assessment (LCA). Although there is a long way to go in integrating FAIR data sharing for LCA, tools and guidelines provided by the FAIR Impact project help to identify data sharing pathways and create channels for communication between experts in different domains to learn from each other."

Skills4EOSC

Aims

The Skills4EOSC project brought together 44 partners across 18 European countries to build a pan-European network of competence centres supporting the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The main aim of the project was to “create an EOSC-ready European workforce” by harmonising training and establishing new professional roles for scientific data management across Europe.

Outputs

Over the course of the project, Skills4EOSC has produced a range of concrete outputs (<https://www.skills4eosc.eu/resources>) and instruments to enable its aims:

- A mapping of professional profiles (e.g. data steward, researcher, policymaker) and the definition of associated MVS (Minimum Viable Skillsets), plus harmonised curricula and learning paths recognised across Europe.

- A “FAIR-by-Design” methodology for learning materials, ensuring training resources are reusable, shareable, and machine- and human-friendly — helping overcome fragmentation in training assets.
- A quality-assurance and certification framework: a standardised soft-certification mechanism for training materials and courses; certification of trainers via a “Train-the-Trainer” (TtT) programme, leading to “Master Trainer” status and issuance of European Digital Credentials.
- Establishment of a European network of Competence Centres (“CCs”) for Open Science and FAIR data across multiple countries, serving as reference points for training programmes, best practices, support services and community building.

Impact and reflections

Skills4EOSC has played a role in placing competences more firmly on the agenda across Europe, particularly by clarifying roles, expectations, and training pathways in research data management. While the ambition of harmonising practices is substantial, Skills4EOSC did initiate a shared language and set of tools that different organisations can build on. A notable aspect was the participation of many different actors — from policymakers to trainers — which helped ensure that competence development was not treated as a siloed activity.

From a Danish perspective, we were especially pleased to see several universities actively contributing, demonstrating a broad national commitment to coordinated skills development, even if full alignment across institutions and countries will take continued effort beyond the project’s timeframe.

4. Ongoing and upcoming EOSC projects with DeIC involvement

ENTRUST

[ENTRUST](#) (European Network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs)) aims to establish a European network of secure computing environments for processing sensitive data. In many EU and partner countries, there is a growing need to provide researchers and authorities access to confidential information without compromising it. TREs are an established practice in several countries, providing a technical and organisational solution to this challenge. The project’s primary task is to develop a common architectural TRE Blueprint, enhancing interoperability across borders, organisations, and research domains. The ambition is that ENTRUST will eventually enable transnational access to sensitive data and/or the execution of federated analysis of sensitive data. A federation with a common legal, operational, and technical framework, as well as agreement on standards, will give participating countries a new opportunity to unlock the untapped potential of Europe’s sensitive data.

Recent project results:

- Participation in the TRE Provider Forum and Open Provider Forum.
- Contribution to T4.1 Survey and Inventory development.
- Participation in WP7/8 Blueprint validation workshop, Utrecht, Netherlands.

- Participation in the ENTRUST General Assembly.

LUMI AI Factory

AI Factories in Europe

[AI Factories](#) are emerging under the AI Continent Action Plan that establishes innovation packages to boost innovation and collaboration in Europe. The analogy of a factory in the context of AI can be understood as a dynamic ecosystem that fosters innovation, development, and collaboration in the field of Artificial Intelligence. Europe's ambition is to compete in the field of AI, while acknowledging that collaboration is key to success. Therefore, the aim is to develop and implement cutting-edge AI models, foster talent, and engage SMEs to collaborate on innovative initiatives and strengthen Europe's data sovereignty.

Currently, 19 AI Factories have been selected across Europe. One of them is [LUMI AI Factory](#) in Finland, of which Denmark is part, represented by DeIC's members. LUMI AI Factory is formed by [six countries](#) that are brought together to build foundations for their national AI ecosystems and strategies in alignment with a coordinated European Plan for AI. Near-term milestones include Machine Learning Operation environments, data-as-a-service propositions, and support for developing trustworthy AI. [Long-term goals](#) aim to launch the LUMI-AI supercomputer and LUMI-IQ quantum AI environment by 2027.

Synergies between EOSC and LUMI AI Factory

The EOSC federation aims at establishing a common data space for research and innovation, by providing researchers with a system to store, process, analyse and reuse research outputs. At the yearly EOSC symposium 2025, the [synergies between EOSC, European High-Performance Computing \(EuroHPC\) and AI Factories](#) were outlined. Focusing on the mutual dependency on open data and data management skills, as well as computing resources and users from public and industry sectors. AI Factories are part of the EuroHPC federation which secures federated and a world-leading supercomputing and quantum computing infrastructure in Europe. The ambition is to enable AI Factories to access European data spaces, enabled by EOSC, to assist users to access and manage the data they need.

Discussions on the synergies between EuroHPC and AI Factories at EOSC 2025 also highlighted the role of SIMPL, an open-source smart middleware solution. SIMPL will enable cloud-to-edge federations and all major data initiatives that are funded by the European Commission. SIMPL middleware will provide agents to connect to data spaces and this way give access to EuroHPC and AI Factories. SIMPL will enable a common search engine behind data spaces, this means, searching may be highly user-friendly and efficient. As well, ensuring presence and metadata management to provide these search capabilities. In terms of timeline for development, the minimum viable product of SIMPL has been already released in 2025, January. Second iteration conducting feasibility studies with ten member states to further mature the thirteen business processes outlined in the [Ana Juan Ferer presentation at EOSC](#). The planned Data Labs associated with the AI Factories will offer high-quality data, services and technical tools for specific areas of interest. Presently it is not entirely clear how access to the Common European Data Spaces fx EOSC, will be established, but DeIC will follow the development closely.

Artificial Intelligence for Science

By establishing AI Factories, the EU Commission aims to put research and innovation in a competitive position for boosting the economy and scientific progress. At the same time, ensuring that AI developed within the EU adheres to data governance control, policy, and ethical principles. Trends of using AI for science are growing globally and span across two main activities – search and discovery. In the time of information overload, AI can support access to knowledge and information; at the discovery phase, AI can help identify patterns in data that may lead to new insights. Detailed AI application areas are described in the bibliometric analysis “[Trends in the use of AI in science](#)”.

The integration of AI Factories, EOSC, and EuroHPC demonstrates Europe’s commitment to fostering innovation while upholding regulatory and ethical standards, ensuring a balanced and forward-looking AI landscape.

Participation in application for EOSC4All (*application under evaluation*)

DeiC, as the coming candidate Danish EOSC node, has been invited to participate in the consortium applying for funding from EU HORIZON-INFRA-2025-01-EOSC-01 [EOSC Nodes with federating capabilities for the EOSC Federation](#). DeiC found the call and the suggested project highly relevant for the ambition of establishing a Danish EOSC node and is therefore now partner in the project proposal – EOSC4ALL.

The EOSC4ALL Consortium is a partnership of 19 organisations representing 11 countries dedicated to transforming the European research landscape by enabling and supporting the development of the EOSC Federation. By lowering entry barriers to become part of the EOSC Federation, EOSC4ALL aims to empower researchers and institutions to access, share, and discover services and research outputs seamlessly and securely across institutional, national, and disciplinary boundaries via deployment of an EOSC Node.

A core feature that the project is pursuing is an implementation framework “EOSC Node-as-a-Service Platform” that aims to standardise EOSC nodes and make their research infrastructure service offerings interoperable. DeiC, as a main participant in the “Roll-out of EOSC Nodes”, will test the framework and deliver services such as EOSC AAI Delivery and Execution as well as Enterprise File Sync and Sharing (EFSS).

5. A selection of current EOSC projects

[ClimateAdapt4EOSC](#)

The FAIR2Adapt project aims to turn environmental and socioeconomic data into actionable knowledge for climate-change adaptation by building an interoperable data-sharing framework by using FAIR Digital Objects. Through a set of case studies and stakeholder engagement, FAIR2Adapt seeks to enable scalable and evidence-based climate adaptation strategies.

[EOSC Data Gems](#)

The DataGEMS project aims to build a next-generation data discovery and management ecosystem that makes diverse datasets discoverable, combinable, and explorable using advanced data management, natural-language processing and machine learning. The platform will be tested through use cases in areas like education, meteorology and language data infrastructure.

[EOSC Data Commons](#)

The EOSC Data Commons project is building a federated, cross-disciplinary infrastructure that gives researchers seamless access to high-quality, interoperable data and services. Between 2025–2028, it will deliver an AI-powered metadata warehouse and discovery service, a tool catalogue and execution framework, FAIR and reproducibility tools, and a federation of trusted data repositories.

[EOSC EDEN & EOSC FIDELIS](#)

The EOSC EDEN project aims to build a Europe-wide framework to select, preserve, and reappraise valuable research data over time — by accessing datasets usage, quality, and societal or scientific benefit — and provide tools and services to support long-term digital curation under the European Open Science Cloud. The FIDELIS project seeks to establish a sustainable European network of trustworthy digital repositories (TDRs), harmonising standards and practices across repositories, and offering training, support and governance so those repositories remain reliable nodes for open science and long-term data preservation.

[EOSC Gravity](#)

EOSC Gravity aims to guide the transition of the EOSC Partnership into a stable, long-term governance and funding framework beyond 2027. EOSC Gravity plans to strengthen and expand the EOSC ecosystem by supporting the creation of new “EOSC Nodes”.

[Lumen EOSC](#)

The Lumen (Linked User-driven Multidisciplinary Exploration Network) project — launched in January 2025 — aims to foster cross-domain collaboration and discovery by building an interoperable “knowledge and data space” connecting four scientific fields: Mathematics, Social Sciences & Humanities (SSH), Earth-System Sciences, and Molecular Dynamics.

[EOSC Raise Suite](#)

The RAISE Suite project builds a one-stop-shop infrastructure using machine-actionable data management plans (ma-DMPs) to deliver “FAIR-by-design” services across the entire research data lifecycle — from collection through to automatic processing and reuse. By integrating the previous EOSC-RAISE platform, RAISE Suite enables data to remain securely with their providers while allowing approved algorithms to process them.

[EOSC AqualNFRA](#)

The AqualNFRA project is building a virtual environment with multi-disciplinary data and services to help scientists and stakeholders work together to restore healthy oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters. It provides tools for storing, sharing, accessing, analysing and processing research data across disciplines and borders by leveraging other data infrastructures. AqualNFRA also includes case studies across regions like the Baltic Sea, North Sea, Mediterranean and pan-European waterways to co-design and test its services.

6. Stakeholder and use case library

DeiC is putting together a data management use case library. Examples of use cases could, for instance, include:

- Implementation of FAIR data management in a certain discipline, or across several disciplines
- Use of data management tools in a specific discipline or/and across disciplines
- Data sharing and interoperability across disciplines
- FAIR data management and tools for sensitive research data

The use cases would be an inspiration for others, not only in Denmark, but also across the EOSC community. In certain cases, we might ask the owners of the use cases to participate in EOSC projects. If you are interested or know anyone who might be interested, please write to deic@deic.dk with the subject line 'Data Management use case'. In the future, we hope and aim to increase participation from Danish universities in EOSC calls.

7. Future plans and reflections

Denmark is committed to EOSC, and to strengthening our national research ecosystem by enabling FAIR data sharing and cross-border scientific collaboration, giving local scientists access to a wider range of data, tools and services while increasing the overall quality, impact and visibility of their work. EOSC fosters interdisciplinary innovation and data-driven science, reducing duplication of effort and accelerating breakthroughs that benefit society and the economy.

As highlighted in the [Crete Declaration](#), FAIR data sharing and strategic collaboration across disciplines provide the robust scientific evidence needed to inform policy and support societal responses to major challenges such as climate change and biodiversity loss. For individual researchers, EOSC also enhances recognition and credit for data, software and other non-traditional research outputs by making them discoverable, citable and reusable across the European research landscape.

The EU Reference Node helps provide a first clear and trusted entry point to EOSC resources. Building on this, a Danish national node would offer a local gateway that supports Danish researchers, as well as researchers in other countries, aligns national infrastructures with EOSC, and strengthens Denmark's role in the broader European open science community.

Realisation of a Danish national EOSC node means that Denmark must be able to both contribute to and make use of the EOSC federation's digital infrastructure, tools, services, and data. Danish digital research assets must be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR), based on EOSC's strategic ambitions for interoperability, standardisation, and technological convergence. In spring 2026, DeiC will present a vision paper to invite feedback and collaboration with national stakeholders for this development.